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Framing Analysis of Nusantara Capital City on Indonesia Environmental Activist Posts at Instagram

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Abstract

Background of the problem: Recently, environmental activists of Indonesia are becoming increasingly aggressive in raising public awareness about environmental issues on social media platforms to highlight environmental problems caused by various factors, including political endeavours. **Purpose:** The focus of this study is to explore the language choices used in the environmental account's posts and express their attitudes toward Nusantara Capital City. **Method:** The data of this study is obtained from one of prominent Indonesia environmental activist account on Instagram, namely greenpeaceid. For highlighting research novelty, this study collects the posts of Nusantara Capital City of Indonesia published from January to September 2024. Moreover, this study uses descriptive qualitative approach to get depth understanding of provided contents. **Result:** This study result found three ideas conveyed by greenpeaceid post regarding Nusantara Capital City, including rushed development, disregard of environmental sustainability and indigenous rights, and neglect of renewable energy solutions. Moreover, they directly blame the Indonesia government who is not able to thoroughly consider the indigenous people living there for years. **Implication:** This research significantly contributes primarily to academics or scholars who are interested in framing analysis studies. It is because this study concerns on analysing Environmental issue that is related with political issue in social media.

Keyword: Framing Analysis; Social Media; Environmental Issue; Indonesia; Capital City

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INTRODUCTION

The relocation of Indonesia's capital city from Jakarta to Nusantara Capital City (NCC) in Kalimantan represents a significant political, economic, and environmental shift. NCC is being constructed to replace Jakarta to address several longstanding challenges faced by the city, such as overpopulation, pollution, and land subsidence (Praditya et al., 2023). However, this large-scale urban planning effort is not without controversy, particularly regarding its environmental and social impacts. The relocation project has faced criticism from environmental groups, who express concerns about the destruction of natural habitats and the displacement of indigenous communities (Mustakim et al., 2023; Nisaa et al., 2023; Praditya et al., 2023).

Moreover, the transformation of vast forested lands into urban infrastructure raises questions about the sustainability of this project. Activists and environmentalists argue that such changes could lead to severe ecological consequences, particularly in a region known for its rich biodiversity. Research by Syaban & Appiah-Opoku (2024) highlights the complexities of land use transition in Indonesia's new capital, indicating the multidimensional conflicts between development and environmental conservation. In addition, Arrozaaq & Firmansyah (2023) emphasize the need for adaptive governance to manage these environmental challenges effectively, warning that without appropriate interventions, the region could face significant environmental degradation.

A general solution to this problem lies in the integration of more sustainable policies that balance the needs of development with environmental protection. According to Praditya et al. (2023), adopting defense strategies that include strict environmental regulations, and sustainable urban planning could mitigate the adverse impacts of the capital's relocation. These strategies involve promoting green infrastructure and ensuring that indigenous communities are properly consulted and compensated. Furthermore, increasing transparency in the governmental decision-making process could help in addressing the concerns of environmental groups, while fostering a more collaborative relationship between the government and civil society.

Recent research on the environmental impact of capital relocation has explored various frameworks to mitigate the negative consequences. For instance, Syaban & Appiah-Opoku (2024) propose a multidimensional conflict analysis approach to address the land use changes in NCC, emphasizing the importance of involving local communities in the planning process. Their study highlights how traditional land rights and environmental concerns must be at the forefront of development efforts to avoid exacerbating social tensions and environmental degradation. The authors argue for a participatory approach that includes indigenous communities in decision-making, thereby reducing potential conflicts.

Another relevant solution comes from studies on air pollution management in Indonesia, which suggest that proactive policies can prevent environmental damage in urban areas. Syuhada et al. (2023) stress the need for stringent air quality regulations and the implementation of sustainable transportation systems as NCC develops. These measures could help in controlling pollution levels, ensuring that the new capital does not replicate the environmental problems faced by Jakarta. Furthermore, Arrozaaq & Firmansyah (2023) discuss adaptive governance strategies to balance the demands of development with environmental preservation. They argue that flexible policy frameworks, capable of adjusting to the evolving environmental conditions, are critical in managing urban expansion in ecologically sensitive areas.

While previous studies have addressed environmental impacts such as air pollution, they have not adequately examined the role of social media in amplifying activist narratives. Studies have yet to explore how activists' discourse shapes public perception of the environmental and social consequences of the project, particularly on platforms like Instagram, which play a crucial role in modern environmental advocacy. The framing of issues by environmental organizations like Greenpeace Indonesia account (*greenpeaceid*) on Instagram and its potential influence on public opinion remains underexplored. This research gap is critical, as social media increasingly becomes a primary source of information for the public, shaping their perceptions of large-scale governmental projects.

Investigating how activists and organizations convey their ideas is crucial because it can reveal the strategies used to construct their messages and highlights how these techniques influence public opinion. Understanding these strategies enables a critical evaluation of whether the framing employed by these entities aligns with reality or distorts the issue to advance specific agendas. Such an analysis is essential to comprehensively assess the effectiveness and accuracy of their communications and the potential impact on policy-making or societal views. Additionally, examining the framing techniques can contribute to broader discussions on media literacy and the role of activism in shaping public discourse.

The objective of this study is to perform a framing analysis of the Greenpeace Indonesia Instagram account, which has been vocal about the environmental and social consequences of relocating Indonesia's capital city to NCC. This research aims to explore how environmental activists utilize language and imagery to present their ideological stance against the project, particularly focusing on the portrayal of the indigenous peoples' land rights and environmental degradation. By analysing Greenpeace Instagram posts, this research provides new insights into how activists shape public discourse on environmental issues, filling a crucial gap in the literature. The study will also contribute to the broader understanding of the role of social media in environmental advocacy, particularly in developing countries.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Framing Analysis

Framing analysis is a methodological tool used to understand how media construct and present reality. It explores how events are selectively presented and organized in order to promote specific interpretations or viewpoints. According to Suharyo (2021) framing is employed to observe how events are understood and organized by the media. Frames highlight certain bits of information, making them more noticeable or memorable for the audience (Entman, 1993, 2007).

Entman's approach to framing analysis revolves around four key functions, namely defining problems, diagnosing cause, making moral judgement, and proposing solution. In defining problem stage, frames identify what is at stake and the costs involved, often in terms of shared cultural values. Then, frames establish who or what is responsible for the problem. after that, it is used to evaluate the actors and their actions, often positioning them in moral terms. Finally, frames propose solutions or responses to the issues highlighted.

Framing not only shapes how audiences understand an issue but also how they emotionally and behaviorally respond to it. According to Ingenhoff & Richner (2019), the framing of issues in a positive or negative light can lead to varying effects based on the

audience's pre-existing beliefs. In the digital age, where social media plays a crucial role in shaping public opinion, framing analysis becomes an essential tool for understanding how narratives around topics like the Nusantara Capital City project are constructed and disseminated across platforms.

Framing Social Media

Social media influencers, which include news organizations, government bodies, nonprofits, and even individuals, play key roles in disseminating information and impacting public interpretations of crises or critical issues (Zhao, 2023). It wields significant power in shaping how people perceive events by selecting and emphasizing certain aspects of an issue while downplaying others. This framing process is crucial because it not only influences how an audience understands a problem but also how they respond to it, whether emotionally or through actions such as advocacy or behavioral change (Zhao, 2023)

The process in social media is particularly important because it allows alternative actors, aside from traditional news organizations, to construct narratives around crisis responsibility and issue interpretation (Muralidharan et al., 2011). In environmental activism, for instance, influential accounts can highlight environmental degradation while assigning blame to specific actors, such as the government or corporations. By framing the conversation around responsibility, these social media influencers empower users to engage with the issue in a manner that might not have been possible through conventional media outlets.

Social media framing works by making certain elements of a topic more salient or noticeable to the audience (Entman, 1993). For example, environmental activists on Instagram may frame the development of Indonesia's Nusantara Capital City as an ecological disaster by repeatedly highlighting the deforestation and displacement of indigenous communities. Such framing not only directs attention to these particular issues but also promotes specific interpretations that influence how followers respond to the posts.

Furthermore, social media's capacity to influence public understanding is deeply intertwined with its ability to emphasize certain frames. Influential on these platforms often select frames that help their audience make sense of complex or multifaceted issues. By focusing on particular aspects of a crisis, such as environmental destruction or social injustice, social media actors can guide their audience toward specific conclusions or actions (Zhao, 2023). This selective framing process shapes not only the audience's comprehension of the problem but also their sense of moral responsibility, often motivating activism or advocacy. Through strategic framing, social media becomes not just a platform for information dissemination but a critical space for shaping public opinion and influencing social behavior.

METHOD

This study used a qualitative method with a specific focus on content analysis. This method is particularly useful in understanding social phenomena in present study because it explored meaning behind the investigated text (Syafri et al., 2023). The research aims to systematically, factually, and accurately describe how environmental activists frame the Nusantara Capital City (NCC) of Indonesia, as expressed through their social media posts. By focusing on the Instagram posts of Greenpeace Indonesia, a prominent environmental organization, this study seeks to

explore how this group presents environmental issues surrounding the development of Indonesia's new capital.

The primary data source for this research is the Instagram account of Greenpeace Indonesia (*greenpeaceid*), focusing on posts related to NCC. Greenpeace Indonesia account was selected because it is an active and influential environmental organization known for its strong stance on environmental issues in Indonesia. This platform is particularly relevant for the study as social media plays a significant role in shaping public opinion and discourse around environmental activism.

In data collection process, this study conducted two steps, namely data identification and data restriction. The data identification was used to identify posts on *greenpeaceid*'s Instagram account that are directly related to the development of the NCC. This initial phase focuses on gathering a comprehensive collection of relevant posts that mention the capital's development. Then, the data restriction was employed to filter the collected posts, narrowing the data set to those that specifically address environmental issues. Posts unrelated to environmental concerns or the capital's development were excluded from the analysis to maintain focus on the environmental framing of the Nusantara project.

After data collection, data analysis process was conducted through four key elements of framing analysis outlined by Entman (2007), including defining problem, diagnose cause, make moral judgement, and treatment recommendations. Entman's theory sees framing as a strategic process of emphasizing certain aspects of reality, and it was used to dissect how Greenpeace Indonesia account frames the environmental challenges posed by the development of the Nusantara Capital City.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Instagram today is one of social media that is mostly used by Indonesia people (Nadira et al., 2023). It is undoubtedly believed as a platform for the users to plainly deliver their thought and feeling. Instagram offers a space for individuals to engage in self-disclosure, where they can share personal experiences and feelings through posts and stories (Mahardika & Farida, 2019). Greenpeace Indonesia (*greenpeaceid*) is one of environment activist that always firmly express their restlessness regarding environment issue, including the environment issue in Nusantara Capital City (NCC).

The data for this study is sourced from the posts on Greenpeace Indonesia's (*greenpeaceid*) Instagram account between January and November 2024. The researcher identified 15 posts related to environmental issues concerning the National Capital City (IKN). However, two posts were excluded from the analysis as they primarily addressed governmental matters, such as budgetary plans and assumptions regarding the 2025–2029 presidential administration. As a result, the total dataset used for this study consists of 13 posts from the *greenpeaceid* Instagram account, all of which focus on the environmental implications of the IKN project. This selection allows for a focused examination of Greenpeace's environmental advocacy related to the relocation of the capital.

Following Entman's theory, present research found several key ideas conveyed by environmental activist, *greenpeaceid*, in their Instagram account regarding environmental issues in NCC of Indonesia:

Rushed Development

In the beginning of 2024, Greenpeace Indonesia frame NCC as a city which has been developed hurriedly. Greenpeace emphasized that the relocation of the capital city would not solve problems in Jakarta such as the air crisis, garbage accumulation, and the risk of sinking, but instead had the potential to increase environmental damage in the new location (East Kalimantan). It is aligned with the location of NCC that is located in one of the largest forests in the world. Consequently, this issue has been the main topic of NCC in the environmental aspect (Kian et al., 2024).

Through its critique of rushed development, Greenpeace stresses the importance of adopting a more inclusive and sustainable approach. They call on the government to first address the pressing issues in Jakarta before moving the capital and to ensure that decision-making processes are more transparent and respectful of local communities' rights. Additionally, Greenpeace advocates for the NCC project to use more environmentally friendly energy sources, moving away from coal, to align with sustainability principles and social justice.

Disregard of Environmental Sustainability and Indigenous Rights

Greenpeace frames the government's actions as prioritizing elite interests over the well-being of local communities and ecosystems, leading to significant social and environmental consequences. A post that has headline "IKN Mau Dibangun Dari Penggusuran" (translated: NCC will be established through expulsion action. IKN (Ibu Kota Nusantara) refers to NCC) in their post explored the construction of a VVIP airport for the IKN project that led to the displacement of local farmers, with nine farmers reportedly arrested without proper legal warrants. Greenpeace points out that this hasty development not only harms the environment but also threatens the livelihoods and human rights of local communities, whose land was forcibly seized without proper legal procedures.

Greenpeace specifically frames the issue as a violation of indigenous land rights, portraying the NCC project as a continuation of historical patterns of exploitation, where indigenous people are forced to vacate their ancestral lands. For instance, in one of the posts that has been published in March 2024, Greenpeace underscores that indigenous communities were given only seven days to leave their homes without adequate compensation or meaningful consultation. This forced eviction, according to Greenpeace, exemplifies how the government's policies are not just environmentally reckless but also socially unjust, as they prioritize economic and political interests over the basic rights of indigenous populations.

The displacement of indigenous communities in favour of development projects like IKN perpetuates a cycle of dispossession and exploitation that these communities have historically faced. Greenpeace uses strong language, such as referring to the IKN project as "colonialism," to highlight the severity of the human rights violations taking place. The moral judgment presented by Greenpeace portrays the government's actions as hypocritical, especially considering the administration's public advocacy for national unity and the preservation of indigenous cultures.

Moreover, Greenpeace argues that these communities, already vulnerable, are being further marginalized by development policies that prioritize economic growth over human rights and environmental conservation. By linking these issues to Indonesia's colonial past and emphasizing the need for genuine independence that includes the protection of indigenous rights, Greenpeace appeals to both ethical concerns and nationalistic sentiments, urging the

public to stand in solidarity with indigenous people against these exploitative development practices.

Neglect of Renewable Energy Solutions

The post published in September 2024 highlights how the public bears the financial burden of this project, through increased taxes and higher costs for services like health assurance, while the benefits of NCC project primarily flow to elites who will enjoy new offices and residences in the relocated capital. In that post, Greenpeace argues that this financial burden exacerbates existing economic inequality, with the majority of citizens receiving no direct benefit from such large-scale infrastructure investments. Furthermore, Greenpeace points to the environmental degradation caused by the NCC project as an additional moral failing, suggesting that the government is not only neglecting the public's financial well-being but also failing to safeguard the environment for future generations.

Consequently, Greenpeace's treatment recommendation advocates for a radical shift in government priorities. They call on the public to demand that the government redirect its spending from high-profile projects to renewable energy initiatives that would address the climate crisis. The urgency of this reallocation should point to the increasing frequency of climate-related disasters in Indonesia, such as floods, droughts, and forest fires. By framing renewable energy development as both a more sustainable and socially just investment, Greenpeace appeals to the public's sense of environmental responsibility and fairness. They believe that Indonesia's future will be better served by focusing on green energy solutions rather than continuing with projects that benefit only a small segment of the population.

Through Entman's framing theory, Greenpeace's critique of the IKN (*Ibu Kota Nusantara*) project is clear. The government's decision to invest heavily in NCC is a misuse of resources that not only neglects urgent environmental concerns but also perpetuates economic inequality. Greenpeace positions renewable energy as the moral and practical alternative, calling for public action to hold the government accountable for its funding choices and to advocate for a more sustainable, equitable approach to development. This framing emphasizes the need for policies that prioritize the climate crisis and the well-being of all citizens, rather than projects that cater to elite interests.

CONCLUSION

Greenpeace Indonesia framed Nusantara Capital City (NCC known as IKN referred to Ibu Kota Nusantara) of Indonesia as serving elite interests, while marginalized groups, such as indigenous and local communities, bear the negative consequences of displacement and ecological harm. This framing highlights the government's failure to balance national development with the protection of vulnerable populations and ecosystems.

Greenpeace presents the government's actions as morally unjust, emphasizing the financial burden on the public and the ecological costs of the project. As a solution, Greenpeace calls for a redirection of funds towards renewable energy and sustainable development practices that prioritize climate action and the rights of indigenous people. They advocate for a more inclusive approach to development that involves local communities in decision-making processes, urging the government to reconsider its approach to ensure long-term environmental and social well-being.

DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTEREST

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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